

Rest and Active Arm Movement Classification Based on Subthalamic Nucleus LFPs for Parkinson's Disease Subtypes

Bruno Leonardo Bianqueti
Center of Engineering,
Modeling and Applied Social
Sciences (CECS)
Federal University of ABC
São Bernardo do Campo,
Brazil
ORCID:000-0002-9355-084X

Julia Baldi de Luccas
Center of Engineering,
Modeling and Applied Social
Sciences (CECS)
Federal University of ABC
São Bernardo do Campo,
Brazil
ORCID:000-0002-5152-9380

Arnaldo Fim Neto
Center of Engineering,
Modeling and Applied Social
Sciences (CECS)
Federal University of ABC
São Bernardo do Campo,
Brazil
ORCID:000-0002-4461-5416

Tiago Paggi Almeida
Division of Electronic
Engineering
Aeronautics Institute of
Technology
São José dos Campos,
Brazil
ORCID:000-0001-5346-6937

Takashi Yoneyama
Division of Electronic
Engineering
Aeronautics Institute of
Technology
São José dos Campos, Brazil

Maria Sheila Rocha
Neurology and Functional
Neurosurgery Division
Santa Marcelina Hospital
São Paulo, Brazil
ORCID:000-0003-4312-3994

Fabio Godinho
Functional Neurosurgery
Division
University of São Paulo
São Paulo, Brazil
ORCID:000-0002-7100-4303

Diogo Coutinho Soriano
Center of Engineering,
Modeling and Applied Social
Sciences (CECS)
Federal University of ABC
São Bernardo do Campo,
Brazil
ORCID:000-0002-9804-7477

Abstract— Adaptive deep brain stimulation (DBS) is expected to improve Parkinson's disease (PD) symptoms. This advance in neurostimulation strategy requires to interact with pathological electrical signaling from basal ganglia circuitry and to use this continuous feedback for controlling therapeutic DBS. Further knowledge about how such signals change in terms of clinical phenotypes and rest/movement states is necessary to optimize this adaptive method and to bridge the clinical needs with daily activities. This work assessed the differences in local field potentials (LFP) spectrum recorded from the subthalamic nucleus (STN) in rest and active arm movement and classified these conditions for the different PD clinical subtypes seeking to estimate the cost underlying the early movement detection. Our results suggest there is a tradeoff between the signal length and accuracy, in which the subtypes play an important role in this performance. These findings may define a crucial design variable for real-time applications and allow future perspectives for tailored DBS design.

Keywords— *Parkinson's Disease; Deep Brain Stimulation; Electrophysiology; Pattern Recognition.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Deep brain stimulation (DBS) is an effective method to control motor symptoms in clinical refractory Parkinson's disease (PD) [1][2]. DBS is recommended when Levodopa administration is not enough efficient or entails side effects such as motor fluctuations, dyskinesia, and cognitive impairment [3]. Therefore, DBS improves the quality of life by reducing PD symptoms and the need for medication in the short and long-term [4]. Despite these benefits, current DBS strategies have some limitations, such as poor control

of some symptoms, adverse effects and excessive energy delivery [5]. This may be partly given to the fact that PD manifests heterogeneous motor and non-motor symptoms, not accounted by the static nature of conventional DBS, which works with fixed electrical parameters [6]. Additionally, conventional DBS does not take into account movement and rest states during daily living activities [7][8][9].

Further efforts have been conducted to propose stimulation protocols of DBS in which stimulation parameters are essentially controlled by local field potentials (LFPs) features from the subthalamic nucleus (STN) [10]. This adaptive DBS (aDBS) aims to drive stimulation parameters by abnormal oscillatory activity recorded from the same electrodes used to stimulate [11][12]. The aDBS provides further economy of battery as well as decreased side effects due to chronic stimulation [10].

Classical LFP rhythms recorded from parkinsonian STN seem to be associated with higher beta power activity (13-35 Hz), which has been suggested as one potential biomarker of Parkinsonian impairment [13]. Nevertheless, it is unknown how Beta and other LFP rhythms differ between distinct PD phenotypes and how movement affects these differences. Furthermore, the time of LFP acquisition necessary to distinguish movement from rest remains unclear.

As these biomarkers are related to the frequency-domain range (e.g., beta band), the present work aimed to investigate the changes in LFP activity between different PD subtypes for guiding future aDBS design. To accomplish

this task, the classification of rest and movement conditions using STN LFP signals were carried out by the estimation of power spectral density associated with the classical LFPs rhythms and the use of such values as features for a binary classification strategy. Additionally, we also analyzed the impact of LFP window size in the classification accuracy, which aims to quantify the cost underlying the early movement detection.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Patients and Data Acquisition

Patients with advanced PD (N=25) were referred by the neurology division at Santa Marcelina Hospital (São Paulo, SP, Brazil) to undergo unilateral or bilateral electrode implantation surgery for deep brain stimulation into the sensorimotor portion of the STN. All patients underwent evaluation for motor impairments using the Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale from Movement Disorders Society (UPDRS/MDS). Based on the evaluation, the patients were divided into the following subtypes: tremor-dominant (TD, N=10), postural instability and gait disorder (PIGD, N=14) and indeterminate (N=1).

Thereby, preoperative magnetic resonance imaging was fused with stereotomography for assisting the physician to set the lead trajectories (separated by 2 mm) towards the STN sensorimotor region, i.e., the definitive target for stimulation [14]. Afterwards, STN LFP for each hemisphere undergoing surgery (n=36, of which TD=14, PIGD=20, indeterminate =02) were acquired from macroelectrode with 1 mm diameter and 1 k Ω impedance (FHC, Greenville, USA), sampled at 24 kHz (bandpass-filtered at 5 Hz - 5 kHz) during 60 seconds in both rest and active arm movement. All patients were awake and after twelve hours of dopaminergic medication washout during the procedure. All the clinical evaluation, surgery, and protocols were performed in agreement with ethical standards (local ethical committee CAAE: 62418316.9.2004.0066). Informed consent was obtained before surgery in all cases.

B. Signal Processing and Feature Extraction

The data were digitally stored for off-line analysis (Lead Point, Minneapolis) and then processed in MATLAB (Mathworks, Inc). Signals were downsampled to 1 kHz, notch filtered for power line noise (60 Hz) and its harmonics, band-pass filtered at 2-400 Hz using IIR Butterworth 6th order filter and z-score normalized.

The signals were segmented by using the Hamming window to reduce edge effect. The procedure was repeated for different window lengths, from 0.5 s to 8 s, with steps of 0.5 s, and overlapped at 50%. This range was chosen to provide at least 2 Hz of spectral resolution.

Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) was evaluated for obtaining frequency representation ($X(f)$) and the power spectral density (PSD) was estimated by $|X(f)|^2$. Then, the power of frequency bands (area under the PSD) was evaluated for the following rhythms: theta (4-8 Hz), alpha (8-13 Hz), beta 1 (13-22 Hz), beta 2 (22-35 Hz), gamma 1 (35-100 Hz), gamma 2 (100-150 Hz) and gamma 3 (150-200 Hz). Figure 1 illustrates the feature extraction in resting condition.

Figure 1: Panel (A) presents the LFP time-domain signal LFP recorded in STN sensorimotor region with 3s window segmentation in resting condition. Panel (B) shows the PSD (dB) until 35 Hz for segment 1 introduced in (A).

C. Classification and Statistical Analysis

We performed the classification of rest and movement conditions for each patient individually. Features were defined by the LFP power in the respective LFP rhythms for each signal segment. Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) classifier was employed with a 10-fold cross-validation scheme for data partitioning.

We hypothesize that the window with 8 s would provide better performance compared with other lengths due to the higher spectral resolution, equal to 0.125 Hz, defining, therefore, the reference for the statistical analysis. The accuracy values of the 8 s window were compared: (1) within the cohort of the same PD subtype considering the different rhythms. Thereby, we applied the analysis of variance and Tukey's multiple comparisons test within each subtype, comparing the band frequencies; (2) for each band, comparing the PD subtypes performance by a two-sample t-test and Mann-Whitney test for normal and non-normal distributions, respectively. Distribution normality was checked by the D'Agostino & Pearson omnibus test.

Statistics of obtained accuracy were also evaluated considering the different window lengths and 8 s window as a reference for comparisons using two-sample t-test for normal distributions and Mann-Whitney test for non-normal distributions. The test aims to identify critical window lengths significantly different from a long-term reference. Significant difference for all tests was considered when $p < 0.05$.

III. RESULTS

Figure 2 illustrates the accuracy distribution for the TD and PIGD subtypes considering the different rhythms for the 8 s window length.

Figure 2: Boxplot for the accuracies of rest vs. movement conditions for TD (blue) and PIGD (red) patients using LDA classifier. * $p < 0.05$

When compared TD vs. PIGD patients' performances for each band frequency, significant differences were found only in gamma 3 power ($p = 0.005$, two-sample t-test). Comparing the patients' performances taking into account the different rhythms, there were no significant differences for neither subtype.

Considering that each patient presents a particular band frequency that best distinguishes rest and movement, Figure 3 shows the performance of the best particular discriminating rhythms in function of the window length. The use of the best LFP rhythm for a specific also emphasizes the requirements to work with customize DBS systems.

Figure 3: Accuracies of rest vs. movement conditions for TD (blue) and PIGD (red) using LDA classifier for different window lengths considering the performances of the best particular discriminating rhythm.

When comparing the 8 s window vs. all other window lengths, we found that the significant differences start at 3 s window for TD patients and at 4.5 s for PIGD patients.

Figure 3 suggests a logarithmically dependence between the accuracy and the window length. Different fit curves were obtained for PD subtypes, being TD described by the

equation 1 ($R^2 = 0.2414$), and PIGD subgroup described by equation 2 ($R^2 = 0.4249$):

$$\text{acc}_{\text{TD}} = 0.171 + 0.704 \cdot \log(x) \quad (1),$$

$$\text{acc}_{\text{PIGD}} = 0.218 + 0.706 \cdot \log(x) \quad (2).$$

Besides the best fit quality obtained for the PIGD cohort, the distribution frequency of best LFP rhythms was also different for each subtype. Figure 4 shows pie charts with the mean percentage of the relative frequency of the best rhythm considering all windows lengths for both TD and PIGD.

Figure 4: Pie chart indicating the percentage of best particular performance rhythm for the PD subtypes.

Higher frequencies seem to provide an improved classification for both subgroups. Considering the ranges within beta (beta 1 and beta 2), beta 1 appeared more times for TD than for PIGD, while the inverse occurs for beta 2.

IV. DISCUSSION

The present work exhibits the LFP rhythms distribution for achieving the best individual movements classification performances and how such distribution changes depending on PD subtype, which may provide important insight for aDBS.

The results suggest that there is no distinction among rhythms for the classification accuracy of rest/movement conditions. Additionally, a high dispersion was observed in the accuracy of all groups. This can be related to the fact that the best classification performance does not concern a single rhythm for all the patients, corroborating the need for a customized protocol.

Despite the obtained variability, the results show a tendency for higher frequency rhythms to be the best discriminators of movement/rest conditions. In fact, some studies suggested that higher frequencies oscillations appear more prominent during movement [15][16], in agreement with the importance of gamma sub band for movement detection. In addition, beta sub bands may also play an important role in this performance depending on the PD subtype. For TD patients, beta 1 was more frequently pointed as the best rhythm for movement/rest classification, whereas PIGD exhibited beta 2 as the one more frequently pointed as the best. For PD patients, event-related desynchronization reduces between 6 and 35 Hz during movement conditions [17][18]. However, how beta band power differs between subtypes is still unclear, although it may be more associated with rigidity and bradykinesia [17][18], but not tremor [19]. Furthermore, comparative

studies of the beta band between clinical subtypes did not consider the movement condition [20]. The present work suggests that best rest *vs.* movement distinction for different PD subtypes may be defined for different beta sub bands.

The results also suggest that there is a tradeoff between window length and accuracy. For “real-time” applications, the shortest possible window length for movement/rest detection is preferred, which would provide instantaneous feedback about the patient's condition. On the other hand, the accuracy may decrease according to our findings as quantified in equations (1) and (2). Therefore, studies to better define the shortest possible LFP duration yet able to identify important electrophysiological phenomena are of great importance. The accuracy *vs.* window length tradeoff may be related to the loss of spectral resolution with window length decrease, providing less accurate power band values. Probably, such tradeoff may define a crucial design variable for adaptive DBS and deserves careful attention.

Moreover, we quantified and observed that windows length for significant accuracy difference from long term behavior (assumed here in 8 s) is different according to the clinical subtypes. These results would support the window's length choice based on the main manifested symptoms. The present work also illustrates, for the first time, that the underlying subtype can influence the tradeoff fit – eqs. (1) and (2) – justifying, once again, the importance for a tailored approach considering patient-specific electrophysiology and any *a priori* available information.

Finally, the results have shown that a single LFP rhythm may not be optimal to discriminate rest/movement conditions, especially when considering the different PD subtypes. Clearly, for TD and PIGD subtypes, beta sub-bands play a different role in achieving the best classification performances, which outlines and requires careful attention for designing more efficient DBS systems.

V. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated that LFPs recorded from the STN can be used to discriminate between rest and movement conditions, which is best performed taking into account the different LFP rhythms for a given patient. The work also established that such discrimination process depends on the window length employed and the patient's clinical symptoms. These findings may provide important insight for future aDBS protocols with a potential impact on a huge population with motor impairment in their daily activities.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Acknowledgments to FAPESP, CNPq, FAPESP BRAINN and Capes for the financially supported and to Santa Marcelina Hospital and Federal University of ABC for contributing and providing the necessary structure for developing this study.

REFERENCES

- [1] DEUSCHL, Günther et al. A randomized trial of deep-brain stimulation for Parkinson's disease. *New England Journal of Medicine*, v. 355, n. 9, p. 896-908, 2006.
- [2] HARIZ, Marwan. Twenty-five years of deep brain stimulation: celebrations and apprehensions. *Movement Disorders*, v. 27, n. 7, p. 930-933, 2012.
- [3] VIDAILHET, Marie. Parkinson disease—symptoms and treatments. *Nature Reviews Neurology*, v. 7, n. 2, p.70-72, fev. 2011.
- [4] CASTRIOTO A, Lozano AM, Poon YY, Lang AE, Fallis M, Moro E. Ten-year outcome of subthalamic stimulation in Parkinson disease: a blinded evaluation. *Arch Neurol*. 2011 Dec;68(12):1550-6. doi: 10.1001/archneurol.2011.182.
- [5] DEUSCHLI G, Schade-Brittinger C, Krack P, et al; German Parkinson Study Group Neurostimulation Section. A randomized trial of deep-brain stimulation for Parkinson's disease. *N Engl J Med*. 2006;355(9):896-908.
- [6] VOLKMANN J, Moro E, Pahwa R. Basic algorithms for the programming of deep brain stimulation in Parkinson's disease. *Mov Disord*. 2006 Jun;21 Suppl 14:S284-9.
- [7] JANKOVIC, Joseph. Parkinson's disease: clinical features and diagnosis. *Journal of neurology, neurosurgery & Psychiatry*, v. 79, n. 4, p. 368-376, 2008.
- [8] OLANOW, C. Warren; STERN, Matthew B.; SETHI, Kapil. The scientific and clinical basis for the treatment of Parkinson disease (2009). *Neurology*, v. 72, n. 21 Supplement 4, p. S1-S136, 2009.
- [9] HERRINGTON, Todd M.; CHENG, Jennifer J.; ESKANDAR, Emad N. Mechanisms of deep brain stimulation. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, v. 115, n. 1, p. 19-38, 2015.
- [10] LITTLE, Simon et al. Adaptive deep brain stimulation in advanced Parkinson disease. *Ann Neurol* p. 449–57, 2013.
- [11] PRIORI, Alberto et al. Adaptive deep brain stimulation (aDBS) controlled by local field potential oscillations. *Experimental neurology*, v. 245, p. 77-86, 2013.
- [12] XU, Cuiping et al. Parkinson's Disease Motor Subtypes Show Different Responses to Long-Term Subthalamic Nucleus Stimulation. *Frontiers In Human Neuroscience*. *Frontiers Media SA*, v. 12, p.1-9, 2018.
- [13] EISINGER, Robert S. et al. A review of basal ganglia circuits and physiology: Application to deep brain stimulation. *Parkinsonism & related disorders*, 2019.
- [14] GODINHO, F. et al. Subthalamic nucleus stimulation in Parkinson's disease. *Journal of neurology*, v. 253, n. 10, p. 1347-1355, 2006.
- [15] CASSIDY, Michael et al. Movement-related changes in synchronization in the human basal ganglia. *Brain*, v. 125, n. 6, p. 1235-1246, 2002.
- [16] KEMPF, Florian et al. Premovement activities in the subthalamic area of patients with Parkinson's disease and their dependence on task. *European Journal of Neuroscience*, v. 25, n. 10, p. 3137-3145, 2007.
- [17] KÜHN, Andrea A. et al. Pathological synchronisation in the subthalamic nucleus of patients with Parkinson's disease relates to both bradykinesia and rigidity. *Experimental neurology*, v. 215, n. 2, p. 380-387, 2009.
- [18] LITTLE, S. et al. Beta band stability over time correlates with Parkinsonian rigidity and bradykinesia. *Experimental neurology*, v. 236, n. 2, p. 383-388, 2012.
- [19] RAY, N. J. et al. Local field potential beta activity in the subthalamic nucleus of patients with Parkinson's disease is associated with improvements in bradykinesia after dopamine and deep brain stimulation. *Experimental neurology*, v. 213, n. 1, p. 108-113, 2008.
- [20] TELKES, Ilknur et al. Local field potentials of subthalamic nucleus contain electrophysiological footprints of motor subtypes of Parkinson's disease. *Proceedings Of The National Academy Of Sciences*, [s.l.], v. 115, n. 36, p.1-10, 21 ago. 2018.